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ВНУТРИОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫЙ МАРКЕТИНГ КАК ЭЛЕМЕНТ СИСТЕМЫ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛОМ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается внутриорганизационный маркетинг как элемент системы стратегического управления персоналом. Исследуются понятия «человеческие ресурсы» и «стратегия» – в контексте управленческой деятельности. Авторами с учетом характерных черт, присущих любой стратегии, представлены особенности стратегического управления. Сделан акцент о наличии взаимовлиянии стратегического управления организации на развитие национальной системы квалификаций и профессиональных стандартов, в первую очередь, развитие и применение профессионального стандарта «Специалист по управлению персоналом» в деятельности хозяйствующего субъекта. На основании изложенного авторами дано определение стратегического управления персоналом и его связь с внутриорганизационным маркетингом.

Ключевые слова: персонал, управление, организация, стратегическое управление персоналом, управление человеческими ресурсами, внутриорганизационный маркетинг

INTERNAL MARKETING AS A SYSTEM ELEMENT OF STRATEGIC PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT

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Annotation: The article deals with the internal marketing as a system element of strategic personnel management. The terms "human resource» and «strategy» are considered in the context of management activity. Taking into account the typical features inherent for any strategy the authors introduce the peculiarities of strategic management. The emphasis is made on presence of mutual influence of strategic management of the organization on the development of National Qualifications Framework and Profession Standards, first of all, on the development of the Standard «The Specialist in Personnel Management» and its application in the activity of a business entity. Based on the considered issues the authors give a definition of strategic personnel management and address its relationship with the internal marketing.

Keywords: personnel, organization, management, strategic personnel management, human resource management, internal marketing

The results of business activities of any organization and its direct competitiveness depend on the personnel as a main source of its prosperity, and it is reasonable to consider the latter as any kind of involved resources from the point of view of its effectiveness and quality of its inherent potential. Employees of an organization set in motion material elements of production, create a product, cost and surplus product in the form of profit. In doing so strategic personnel management plays an important part as providing to a large extent optimal interaction of an enterprise both with its workers inside and with outside environment.

The given research considers the issues of development of strategic personnel management from the point of view of internal marketing. According to I.S. Neganova, «the internal marketing presents systematic actions for use of marketing methods within the organization directed to overcoming of personnel opposition for changes, motivation and cross-functional integration of employees in order to realize the strategy of satisfying customers effectively through creation of motivated and customer focused personnel» [1, с. 211].

Formation of effective internal marketing as an element of strategic management system ensures competitiveness of an enterprise. But first of all, it is necessary to study out the term «strategic personnel management» and its relationship with «internal marketing».

«Internal marketing» as a new term was introduced as an interdisciplinary science at the intersection of management, personnel business and knowledge business, as well as marketing and competitiveness management. There are no great differences in the interpretation of the term; nevertheless, researchers distinguish four approaches to the definition [Ibid.]:

- 1) the system of interrelations of an enterprise with its personnel;
- 2) the system, the process and the mechanism of management of an enterprise's internal market management;
- 3) the philosophy of market orientation of an enterprise;
- 4) the way of practical realization of a new strategy of an enterprise.

As for the concept «strategic management», the results of the carried out analysis of scientific publications show that there are many points of view on the given aspect of management, and the published researches do not give a definite answer on advantages and disadvantages of use of one or another methodology.

The concept «personnel management strategy» began to form in the late 1970s – early 1980s in the Western Europe in rather difficult economic conditions which were due to slowing down of integration and economic growth. As a result of these processes a need arose for further development of management theory, introduction of a new approach to personnel management of organizations, as well as widening of the sphere of strategic personnel management [2, c. 546]. Most researches of this field associate the beginning of study of the issue of strategic personnel management significance with publication of the work «Framework of strategic human resource management» (1984) by C.J. Fombrun who supposed that human resource management and organization structure management are based on the organization's mission and strategy which allows achieving its goals [3, c. 43].

For the last two decades the conceptual approach to the strategic personnel management has been formed in the works of European researchers through convergence and further crossing of spheres in the process of interaction of strategic management and strategic human resource management [4, c. 8].

«Strategic personnel management» as a direction of science and practice has been developed under the influence of general theory of management, strategic management and personnel management proper, therefore it needs concretization and clarification in the context of formation both as theoretical approaches and from the point of view of practical realization in the course of business activity. Without delving into etymology of the term «strategy» it is necessary to note that the word is of Greek origin and means literally «the art of troops deployment in the battle» or the highest degree of the art of war. But for the last few decades the term

has become popular having been introduced into the theory and practice of management so organically that for modern managers this word means the highest demonstration of management activity [5, с. 132].

As the experts note [6, с. 52], the personnel management strategy is among the key functional strategies of an organization. One of the peculiarities of the given approach is that personnel management strategy acquires more and more weighty in the process of its realization. Ensuring the development of the organization in its strategic perspective the factor of human resource becomes the central factor directly accumulating all the results (both positive and negative) on the subtotals of organization's activity.

Some experts have also noted that the defining of the term has been the challenge for big scientific discussion results of which still remain controversial. More detailed interpretations of the concept «personnel management strategy» in the works of home and foreign authors are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Interpretations of the concept «personnel management strategy» in the works of home and foreign authors

Definition of the concept «personnel management strategy»	Refrence
A general plan of measures of an enterprise in the field of personnel work which determines forms and directions, sources and ways of personnel recruiting to ensure achievement of strategic goals of development of the organization.	I.V. Balabanova [7]
Complex of common needs of an organization and personnel satisfied simultaneously by means of realizations of definite procedures and programs or their recruiting.	D. Mann, B. Webb [8]
A control method combining a balance of employees' interests and organization's potential from the point of view of program thinking	V. Maslov [9]
Achievement of long-term goals of an organization through uncovering of labour potential having competitive advantages which are adequate to the changes occurring both inside organization and outside.	L.V. Ivanovskaya [10]
Purposeful activity for meeting the needs of the organization in qualified, loyal and highly motivated employees who are able to provide stable competitive advantage of the organization.	S.I. Sotnikova, E.V. Maslov, N.N. Abakumova> Y. A. Masalova V.P. Osipov [11]

Thus, the common features for most interpretations of the concept «personnel management strategy» are the following:

- long-term character;
- focus on generating new or improving current psychological and motivational, structural consequences characterizing the system of management as a whole or its single elements;
- the goals of strategic personnel management must correspond to the general strategy of the organization development, contribute to the achievement of the goals of development and do not conflict with them;
- strategic personnel management must take into account the interaction between factors of internal and external environment of the organization, which can cause the necessity of correction of general strategy of the organization development and thereafter changes of the personnel composition in number and functionality, variability of combinations its skills and qualifications, style and methods of personnel management.

In order to survive in the competitive struggle in modern conditions enterprises have to develop not only a long-term strategy of their activity but also that of personnel management. At the same time personnel management strategy is developed individually for every organization taking into account the specific character of their activities, goals and plans of the production and influence of the external environment.

Though the concepts «personnel management» and «human resources management» are often considered to be synonyms, the conducted analysis of literary sources allowed concluding that the given concepts differ greatly. For example, in our opinion, human resources management is intended to the development of personnel policy, but personnel management means everyday work with the staff.

The term personnel management is used further in the text as exactly reflecting the HR activities. The slogan «Cadres are all-important» is in demand again. Business owners and administrators understand that it is personnel that become significant resource creating competitive advantage under market conditions.

The Profession Standard «The Specialist in Personnel Management» approved by the order of the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of the Russian Federation 06.10.2015 №691n helps in development and realization of personnel management strategy. According to the document, the main goal of the proper kind of professional activities is «ensuring the efficient operating of personnel management system in order to achieve the goals of the organization», and one of generalized labour functions sounds like «strategic personnel management of the organization». An officer of the personnel management

department (personnel department, human resources management service) is in charge for development and realization of the strategic personnel management system, as well as processes of administration.

That is why a top manager is responsible for the development of the strategic personnel management system which includes the following activities – analysis of successful corporate practices in organizing strategic personnel management of the organization, organizational design and interaction of subdivisions, setting the strategic goals of personnel management, development of corporate policy, plans, programs, procedures and technologies for personnel management; development of corporate culture and social policy, systems of motivation, efficiency, assessment and development of staff; formation of the pay and work organization system; organizational structure development, planning the demand in organization personnel; development of programs and principles of standardization, unification, automation of personnel management processes and safe labour conditions; staff budgeting, creating the technologies for auditing work with personnel and controlling [12].

Therefore, taking into consideration the analysis carried out it can be argued that the personnel management strategy is a conceptual model including everyday solution of short-term tasks (i.e. practical) and development of long-term perspective actions (i.e. strategic) which can be fulfilled in order to achieve the intended perspective goals of the organization in the form of stable competitive advantages by means of motivational effect on the personnel work basing on implementing the programs of self-development and constant improvement of professional qualities of every team member in changing market conditions.

Strategically successful development of personnel contributes to effective solution of main tasks in the interests of the organization (increase of its profitability), as well as in the interests of an employee him (herself) (welfare growth and quality of working life). Here it is worthwhile to mention the concept of «internal marketing» as employee's interests and his or her loyalty increase competitiveness of the organization.

Summing up the conclusion should be done that when working out the strategy of personnel development it is necessary to keep in mind aspects of the internal marketing such as professional competences of employees, high labour motivation and loyalty strengthening, integration of enterprise's functional strategies.

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